

TRADITIONS OF “MASTER AND STUDENT” AND ITS HISTORICAL AND MODERN VIEWS

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Abstract. *The article talks about a number of thinkers who worked according to the Master-student values and had their own tradition. It is known that the educational system includes the activities of teachers and students. The activities of the teacher and the activities of the students are interrelated, but the educational activities of the teacher and the educational activities of the students are distinguished by well-known differences. For example, information is given about the organization of practical training in the form of a group with the teacher, as a rule, working simultaneously with all the students.*

Keywords: *master-student, education, research, knowledge, skill, modern education, social group, models, intellectual potential, tradition.*

At the moment, our country is striving for fundamental changes in the educational and socio-cultural spheres, the need for which is related to changes in thinking, setting goals and forms of actions, as well as the prospects of the economic sector.

The importance of harmoniously and systematically changing these areas is reflected in the educational system, which sets two main goals for all educational institutions: to ensure the global competitiveness of education and the development of people's education. raising a well-developed and socially responsible person based on spiritual and moral values and cultural traditions.

These goals cannot be achieved without creating a system of support and development of skills, talents and competencies. This system should also contribute to solving the problem of self-determination and career guidance of all students.

The most effective strategy that meets the above-mentioned goals and tasks is the use of the "Teacher-student" methodology, within the framework of which it is possible to provide comprehensive support to students of different levels and forms of education.

President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his speech at the ceremony held in connection with the Day of Teachers and Trainers, spoke about the need to establish the "Master-Student" system in order to improve the quality of education. "Today, every teacher and trainer, university teachers who can apply the latest positive innovations in the field of education and science to educational processes, possess deep knowledge and outlook, in a word, should be the most advanced representatives of our time and society. He said that "Our children, educated by such teachers, will grow into a generation capable of creating the bright future of Uzbekistan that we dream of".

There is no doubt that the "Master-student" method will give the expected result in the teacher's work on himself and improving his pedagogical skills. Because teacher-apprenticeship has been a feature of our people's nature since time immemorial, and turning it into a system is of great importance in increasing the effectiveness of education. That is why it is very important to firmly establish the tradition of "Teacher-student" in the education system. In the "Concept of Continuous Spiritual Education" it was determined that the restoration of the traditions of "Teacher

- student" is defined as an important task of implementing spiritual education in the educational system.

Issues of ideological preparation are extremely important in the "Master-student" system. The stronger the student's political consciousness, ideological preparation, culture of thought, the more solid ground is prepared for him to "surpass his teacher" in the future. In order to create such a ground, the teacher himself must have strong knowledge and skills. It was not for nothing that the great Aristotle said that "a student who chases those who have gone ahead and does not wait for those who are left behind will achieve everything."

The tradition of "teacher-student" is not only a narrow method aimed at the development of education, it is first of all a noble idea to make the society prosperous and happy by perfecting the individual. Especially, this idea acquires a more complete meaning when it is nourished by Islamic philosophy. The works of our great ancestors Ibn Sina, Beruni, Farabi, Alisher Navai, hadiths of Imam Bukhari, and Bahauddin Naqshband's principle "Dil ba yoru, dast ba kor" contain valuable wisdom about this noble idea. Many symbols of mentorship were created in the work of our thinking ancestors.

In fact, during the development of the educational system, the growth of intellectual potential in Eastern and Western countries has developed in its own way. This process created the new progressive traditions of the educational system in ancient India, the Brahmins and Gurus, Confucius in China, Socrates' School in Greece, Plato's Academy, Aristotle's Lyceum, the Baghdad Ma'mun Academy or the Khorezm Ma'mun Academy in the Middle Ages.

The immortal values of the "master-student" tradition can be analyzed in the form of Socrates and his disciples. His aphorisms "Power is in knowledge", "The more I know, the more I know I don't know", "Know yourself" are still very relevant today. Socratic schools are the Greek philosophical schools formed by his students and followers in the 5th century BC: Plato's Academy, the Megarian School, the Elida-Eretrean School, the Cerene School, and the stream of Cynics.

Respect and reverence for the teacher as a high value is vividly expressed in the works of Plato. In his "Dialogue of the Socratics", he tries to accurately reflect the views of his teacher, to systematically and comprehensively promote his ideas. While leading the academy he founded for nearly forty years, he also constantly propagates his mentor's views. The fact that this tradition has been preserved during the more than 900 years of activity of Plato's Academy shows that Socrates did not become the spiritual teacher of all mankind for nothing.

The 8th-11th and 15th centuries are recognized as the Eastern Renaissance in human history. During this period, the scientific researches of the scientists who lived and worked in the regions of our country were conducted in the scientific and educational centers in Baghdad, Marv and Khorezm. Our compatriots made a great contribution to the development of secular and religious sciences in scientific schools established in the Middle Ages. As a result, the generations of Bukhari, Ferghani, Khorezmi, Termizi, Samarkandi left an indelible mark in the history of humanity with their great scientific innovations based on the continuation of the "teacher-student" tradition.

The main didactic achievement of Socrates is a dialogic argument that leads to the truth with the help of questions thought up by the teacher. The teacher should awaken the strong spiritual aspects of the student and help him to create himself.

In Plato's opinion, the role of teacher can be trusted, first of all, to older people. In this regard, according to J.J.Rousseau, the most important and difficult art of a teacher is to know not to do anything with a student.

At the beginning of the 20th century, K.D.Ushinsky also expressed his thoughts about the problems of mentoring. He emphasizes that one should not brag about one's experience, one should not be proud of counting the years of one's educational activity, and advises one not to fall into the mistaken opinion that professional experience covers the lack of theoretical training.

The written monuments of the people of the East are in the books "Panchatantra", "Kalila and Dimna", "Avesta", "Wisdoms" of Confucius, "The Book of Science" by Abu Hamid Ghazali, "The Master-Student" in the work "Futuvvatnomai Sultaniya" by Husayn Vaiz Koshifi. Eastern values of his mother are expressed.

It is known that the educational system includes the activities of teachers and students. The activities of the teacher and the activities of the students are interrelated, but the educational activities of the teacher and the educational activities of the students are distinguished by well-known differences. For example, in the group form of organizing practical training, the teacher, as a rule, works with all students at the same time. Mastering the teacher's instructions, forming knowledge, skills, personal qualities, worldview by the students happens individually for each student, depending on his mental and physical development, initial preparation, interest in learning, willful qualities and other characteristics. Iadi All this requires the teacher to use such methods of educational activity that take into account the individual characteristics and differences of each student as much as possible, that is, if the requirements for the activity of each student in the lesson correspond to his capabilities, such conditions of the educational process creation pays off.

Today, Hasan Basri's "Without scientists, people would be like animals", "Scientists are like stars. If it is visible, people will find their way with their help. If they disappear from sight and remain in the dark, they will wonder where to go," is very important.

One of the main features of modern education should be considered to be the transition from the paradigm of knowledge to competence. Rejection of the knowledge-based approach to education in favor of the competency-based approach is related to the actual problems of modernizing the modern education system with attention to the new world standards.

Research on mentoring in our country shows that many educational and business organizations consider mentoring as a strategically important element of the system. They emphasize the task of developing students and teachers not only the ability to adequately acquire knowledge, skills and abilities acquired through education, but also the ability to independently form new skills and abilities. As a result, mentor-apprenticeship models themselves are changing: the possible composition of mentor-apprentice relationship participants, the scope of mentor-apprenticeship, the interaction process itself, and the range of problems solved with its help are expanding.

Mentorship is a universal technology for building experience, knowledge, skills, competencies, meta-competencies and values through informal, mutually enriching communication based on trust and partnership.

The form of mentor-apprenticeship is a method of implementing a target model by organizing the work of a mentor pair or individual group in a specific role situation determined by the main activity and the position of the participants.

Depending on the conditions of implementation of mentor-apprenticeship, it is divided into the following forms: "apprentice-apprentice", "teacher-teacher", "student-apprentice", "employer-apprentice", "employer-student". Each of these forms involves solving a certain set of tasks and problems using a single mentor-apprenticeship methodology, partially modified taking into account the stage of training / professional activity and the initial basic requirements of the three participants of the system.

In order to qualitatively present the characteristics of different forms of mentor-apprenticeship, it is necessary to consider the task of problems solved with the help of mentor-apprenticeship and the existing system in each individual case.

The following problems of a student of a higher educational institution are solved with the help of a mentor-apprenticeship:

- * low motivation for studying and self-development, poor academic performance, lack of high-quality self-management;
- * lack of a conscious position necessary for choosing an educational trajectory and carrying out professional activities in the future;
- * the impossibility of high-quality self-awareness within the curriculum;
- * lack of conditions for forming an active citizenship position;
- * low awareness of the prospects of self-selection of creative development, career and other opportunity vectors;
- * identity crisis, destruction or low level of value and life positions and orientations;
- * conflict that hinders horizontal and vertical social movement, underdeveloped communication skills;
- * lack of conditions for the formation of meta-science skills and meta-competence;
- * the upper limit of access to educational programs, programs for the development of talented students;
- * psychological crises associated with the general difficulties of adolescence against the background of a decrease in emotional stability, a lack of clear prospects for the future and regular high-quality support;
- * Adaptation problems in the (new) educational team: psychological, organizational and social.

At the moment, state educational standards fully cover the need to form basic and professional competencies that do not meet the challenges of time and require the involvement of representatives of production or business. In this regard, within the competence approach, a new task - formation of meta-competencies should be defined.

It is important to consider the range of problems to be solved at the level of the region, which is the main initiator of the development of the updated system of education and vocational training of students, as well as through mutual cooperation.

Comprehensive presentation of the scope of these tasks will help educational institutions to receive comprehensive support for their initiatives from the regional administration and public understanding of the need to introduce new approaches.

So, among the main problems:

- * low educational, sports and cultural results of individual educational institutions;
- * job security of young people, which leads to a decrease in the standard of living, an increase in disadvantages and the migration of valuable workers to other regions;

* devaluing young people leads to both deviant and neutral behavior in terms of civic participation;

* lack of communication between different levels of education in the region;

* lack of support system for talented young people in the region;

* obsolescence of labor reserves leads to inertia of regional enterprises, decrease in the number of initiatives and innovations, and decrease in work efficiency.

With the help of introducing mentor-apprenticeship programs in regional educational institutions and enterprises, it is possible to achieve comprehensive improvement of educational and economic results. Also, what is important at the interpersonal and social levels, in this way it is possible to form stable methods of interaction between individual systems and generations, and a sense of belonging to the life and development of the region.

Each of the five forms of mentoring is discussed below, which allows creating a complete understanding of the participants of the interaction, the goals and objectives of each of the parties, as well as the measurable results and forms of evaluating the effectiveness of the program.

The mentor-apprenticeship forms mentioned above can become an effective environment for the formation of a new educational strategy aimed at developing necessary skills, practical skills and meta-competencies. That is:

* for quality implementation of personnel policy;

* organizational transition to the system of professional and personal self-determination;

* development of human capital and potential of the youth of our country.

The organization of work in all five forms does not require spending a lot of money, because all programs include the use of internal resources of the regions (employees, specialists), in addition to attracting specialists for the initial training of teachers.

Each of the presented forms solves the specific tasks of all participants of the teacher-student interaction: at the individual level (teacher and student), at the organizational level (educational institution or enterprise) and at the regional level. The planned results of the implementation of the master-apprenticeship programs cover almost all the main problem areas of the modern system - from educational tasks to the issues of prosperity and economic development of the region.

The system of mutual communication of forms of master-apprenticeship creates a wide pedagogical and professional movement in our country, including representatives of various social groups, institutions and generations in a single team, whose efforts contribute to the development of the educational and economic systems of Uzbekistan as a whole.

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